

Between the Mirror and the Camera: Reading the Social Media Self as a Character

Abstract: With the modernisation of scientific technologies, the idea of “text” is extending to a degree where along with printed content or visual content like films, Social media too is attracting scholars’ attention from various disciplines. Characters, therefore, are no more apolitically fictive, summoned to embody their author's psychology and ideology. Rather, it is complex and layered, especially in the context of the projection of the 'self'. As a part of popular culture today, social media promotes an alternative “way of being” which requires critical attention. The difference between the mirror and the camera, between reflection and projection - is almost always associated with the exo-teleological manifestation of the self. Aggrandizement of this alternate virtual self as a character in such platforms is informed with the audience's reception (telos in this case). Creating a character out of the self is, therefore, bound to be the product of a conflict between the internalisation of the identity and the externalization of the self. In this paper, my concern is about characterising the self-image on various social media with a particular focus on the queer male ‘influencers’ creation of it on such platforms and their use of drag. We need to critically address whether it is merely a medium of “getting out of the closet” or any other nuanced politics are in operation and also how, in this particular context, it affects the self-image characterology.